

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 5

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 5

Бош муҳаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети Илмий ишлар ва инновациялар бўйича
проректори, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi

*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

*тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Очилов Улугбек Усмонович

*PhD, доцент, СамДТУ Дипломдан кейинги таълим
факултети Психиатрия курси мудири. СамДТУ Илмий
кенгаши котиби. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Шавази Наргиз Нуралiena

*DSc. Доцент, СамДМУ 3-сон акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович

*Тоҷикистон Давлат тиббиёт университети Онкология
ва нур таъхиси кафедраси мудири, Тиббиёт фанлари
доктори, Профессор, Душанбе, Тоҷикистон.
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Сандов Сандамир Аброрович

*тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалжанов Ойбек Абдуҷаббарович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар
тери-таносил касалликлари ва ОИТС
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касалликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, проректор по научной работе и инновациям Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического госпиталя Сеульского национального университета, Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины Ташкентской медицинской академии
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очилов Улугбек Усманович

PhD, доцент, заведующий курсом психиатрии факультета постдипломного образования СамГМУ. Секретарь Ученого совета СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc. доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Рашид Захидович

Заведующий кафедрой Онкологии и лучевой диагностики Таджикского медицинского университета, д.м.н., профессор, Душанбе, Таджикистан
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Саидов Сандамир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии, неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Vice-Rector for scientific work
and Innovation, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shaykatovna
PhD Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine, Tashkent
Medical Academy. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich

*PhD, Docent, Head of the Psychiatry Course at the Faculty of
Postgraduate Education of SamSMU. Secretary of the Academic
Council of SamSMU. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Shavazi Nargiz Nuraliyena

*DSc, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Obstetrics
and Gynecology N 3 of Samarkand State Medical University.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Yuldashev Ravshan Zakhidovich

*Head of the Department of Oncology and Radiation Diagnostics
at Tajik State Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Dushanbe, Tajikistan <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Department of Dermatovenerology,
pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **Shukrullayeva G.J., Axmedov A.A.**
THE CONDITION AND FEATURES OF HARD TISSUES OF TEETH DURING PREGNANCY.....10
2. **Vokhidov E.R.**
ASSESSMENT OF DENTAL STATUS AND ORAL HEALTH IN PREGNANT WOMEN.16
3. **Kuliev O.A., Karabaev A.G.**
PATHOGENETIC BASIS OF REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM DISORDERS IN THE POST-INTENSIVE CARE PERIOD.....21

THERAPY

4. **Musayeva L.J., Yakubov A.V., Zufarov P.S., Abdusamatova D.Z., Saidova Sh.A., Pulatova N.I.**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF REBAMIPID IN THE TREATMENT OF FUNCTIONAL DYSPEPSIA.....26
5. **Yakubov A.V., Musayeva L.J., Akbarova D.S., Saidova Sh.A., Aripdjanova Sh.S., Avazova G.N.**
THE CURRENT ROLE OF MACROLYDES IN THE TREATMENT OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA.....31
6. **Khasanjanova F.O., Mamatova N.T.**
ASSESSMENT OF RENAL DYSFUNCTION IN YOUNG PATIENTS WITH ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME AS AN INDEPENDENT PREDICTOR OF DISEASE PROGNOSIS.....37
7. **Makhmudova N.M.**
PHYTOTHERAPY OF DYSPEPTIC SYMPTOMS IN PATIENTS WITH H. PYLORI-ASSOCIATED CHRONIC GASTRITIS USING THE DIETARY SUPPLEMENT VENTRAP.....43

SURGERY

8. **Kurbaniyazov Z.B., Mukhiddinov B.X., Askarov P.A.**
ASSESSMENT OF RENAL DYSFUNCTION IN YOUNG PATIENTS WITH ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME AS AN INDEPENDENT PREDICTOR OF DISEASE PROGNOSIS.....50
9. **Makhmudov T.B., Sherbekov U.A., Kurbaniazov Z.D.**
PROGNOSTIC FACTORS FOR CHOOSING THE VOLUME OF OPERATION IN TOXIC FORMS OF GOITER.....59
10. **Makhmudov T.B., Sherbekov U.A., Kurbaniazov Z.D.**
EFFICIENCY OF PLASMAPHORESIS IN PREOPERATIVE PREPARATION OF PATIENTS WITH SEVERE THYROTOXICOSIS.....69
11. **Mardonov B.A., Kurbaniyazov Z.B., Rakhmanov K.E.**
COMPLEXITY AND FEATURES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF POSTCHOLECYSTECTOMY SYNDROME.....78
12. **Egamberdiyev A.A.**
ENDOVIDEOSURGICAL METHODS FOR THE TREATMENT OF ESOPHAGEAL HIATAL HERNIAS.....84
13. **Abdullayev S.A., Xudoynazarov U.R., Boysariyev Sh.U.**
PROBLEMS OF TREATMENT OF PURULENT-INFLAMMATORY COMPLICATIONS OF SOFT TISSUES IN SINDROME DIABETES MELLITUS FUT.....89

14. **Daminov F.A., Bobokulov A.U.**
PATHOGENETIC ANALYSIS OF GASTRODUODENAL ULCER (LITERATURE REVIEW).....94
15. **Jurayev O.U., Kurbaniyazov Z.B., Khursanov Y.E.**
CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE VARICOTROMBOPHLEBITIS AND RESULTS RESEARCH VENOUS SYSTEMS LOWER LIMBS.....101
16. **Shonazarov I.Sh., Oblokulov Z.T.**
THE NATURE OF THE MICROFLORA OF THE ABDOMINAL CAVITY DEPENDING ON THE PH VALUES IN PERFORATED DUODENAL ULCER.....108
17. **Shonazarov I.Sh., Oblokulov Z.T.**
OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT TACTICS IN PATIENTS WITH PERFORATED DUODENAL ULCER.....113
18. **Raxmatov B.X., Xujabaev S.T.**
CHOICE OF SURGICAL INTERVENTION IN CHRONIC HAEMORRHOIDS.....122
19. **Raxmatov B.X., Xujabaev S.T., Dusiyarov M.M.**
DYNAMICS OF THE WOUND PROCESS AFTER HAEMORRHOIDECTOMY.....126

PEDIATRICS

20. **Garifullina L.M.**
FEATURES OF FORMATION OF RISK FACTORS FOR THE EMERGENCE OF METABOLIC SYNDROME IN CHILDREN WITH ABDOMINAL OBESITY.....133
21. **Yuldashev B.A., Murodova M.D.**
SUBJECTIVE AND OBJECTIVE CLINICAL SYMPTOMS OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISORDERS IN CHILDREN WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE.....140
22. **Begnaeva M.U., Siddikov O.U.**
INCIDENCE AND RISK FACTORS OF DRUG POISONING IN CHILDREN.....146
23. **Ulugmuratov A.A.**
EFFECTIVENESS OF ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY FOR INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION IN CHILDREN.....152

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

24. **Ibragimov D.D., Boymuradov Sh.A., Baratova Sh.N.**
INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATING PATIENTS WITH COMBINED INJURIES OF FACIAL BONES WITH ASSESSMENT OF THE HYGIENIC CONDITION OF THE ORAL CAVITY.....156
25. **Islamova N.B.**
INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF DENTAL REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH COMPLETE ADENTIA.....163
26. **Khanazarov D.A.**
ON THE ISSUE OF ODONTOPREPARATION IN ORTHOPEDIC DENTISTRY.....168

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

27. **Mirdjurayev E.M., Samiyev A.S., Bobomurodov G.A.**
INNOVATIVE METHODOS FOR REHABILITATION OF STROKE COMPLICATIONS.....178
28. **Muzaffarova N.Sh., Shirinov Sh.U.**
THE COURSE OF HEADACHE IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC STROKE.....183

29. **Xudaybergenov N.Y., Kilichev I.A., Adambaev Z.I., Samiyev A.S.**
INFLUENCE OF GEOMAGNETIC ACTIVITY ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF BRAIN STROKES.....188
30. **Sabirov D.M., Eshonov O.Sh., Batirov U.B., Khaydarova S.E.**
MONITORING OF HEMATOLOGICAL INDICES IN PREDICTING OUTCOMES IN CEREBROVASCULAR CRITICAL CONDITIONS.....192
31. **Umirova S.M.**
CORRECTION OF DIABETIC POLYNEUROPATHY NIVALIN WITH PHARMACOPUNCTURE METHOD.....199
32. **Khakimova S.Z.**
REDUCING THE INTENSITY OF COMPLICATIONS WITH THE HELP OF REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH PARKINSON'S DISEASE.....205
33. **Haydarova S. Kh., Sharipov R.Kh., Mavlyanova Z.F., Xudoyqulova F.**
FEATURES OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF LONG-TERM EFFECTS OF PERINATAL LESIONS OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM.....210

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

34. **Lutfullaev U.L., Kobilova Sh.Sh., Safarova N.I., Madaminova N.E.**
PREDICTORS OF CLINICAL OUTCOME IN SENSORINEURAL HEARING LOSS.....219
35. **Lutfullaev U.L., Kobilova Sh.Sh., Safarova N.I., Madaminova N.E., Zoirov O.T., Buronov F.Y., Makhamov Kh.O.**
EFFECTIVENESS OF PROLONGED ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY IN CHILDREN WITH EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA.....226
36. **Raupova K.M., Nasretdinova M.T.**
PROFESSIONAL HARDNESS OF HEARING UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF THE STRONG INTERRUPTED NOISE.....235
37. **Nasretdinova M.T., Xayitov A.A., Dustboboyev D.S., Normurodov N.A.** MANAGEMENT OF OTITIS MEDIA WITH EFFUSION IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES.....241
38. **Nasretdinova M.T., Xayitov A.A., Dustboboyev D.S., Normurodov N.A.**
CHRONIC EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA IN CHILDREN: CYTOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF CONFIRMATION OF STAGES OF THE DISEASE.....248
39. **Nasretdinova M.T., Omonova M.Sh.**
MICROFLORA IN CHRONIC POLYPOUS SINUSITIS.....255
40. **Nasretdinova M.T., Omonova M.Sh.**
MANAGEMENT OF CHRONIC POLYPOUS RHINOSINUSITIS.....261

ONCOLOGY AND RADIOLOGY

41. **Boyko E.V., Tychiev A.P.**
RESULTS OF TRIMODAL THERAPY FOR INVASIVE BLADDER CANCER.....265
42. **Xamidov O.A.**
CURRENT STATE OF MEDICAL RADIOLOGY IN THE WORLD.....270
43. **Jumanov Z.E., Xamidov O.A., Beknazarova X.N.**
MODERN METHODS OF VISUALIZATION OF GALLBLADDER DISEASES.....295
44. **Raximov N.M, Shaxanova Sh.Sh, Raxmonov K.A.**
S100 PROTEIN EXPRESSION AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN DISSEMINATED BREAST CANCER.....302
45. **Urozov N.E., Vypova N.L., Nishanov D.A., Madaliyev A.A., Ibragimov Sh.N., Enikeeva Z.M.**
STUDY OF TOXICOLOGY OF THE ANTITUMOR DRUG KOLKHIPRIT-NEO (K-20).309

46. **Ulmasov F.G., Esankulova B.S.**
IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL STUDY OF THE OVARIAN CANCER
MICROENVIRONMENT AT DIFFERENT STAGES: THE ROLE OF IMMUNE CELLS IN
TUMOR PROGRESSION.....318
47. **Akramov A.R.**
DYNAMICS OF INCIDENCE, AGE AND MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES PRIMARY
BRAIN TUMORS ACCORDING TO THE DATA OF THE SAMARKAND BRANCH
RSSPMC ONCOLOGY AND RADIOLOGY.....322

MORPHOLOGY

48. **Yusupova N.A., Oripov F.S.**
NON-INVASIVE DIAGNOSIS OF FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN THE GASTRIC UNDER
THE INFLUENCE OF ENERGY DRINKS.....328
49. **Kim T.A., Mavlyanova Z.F., Tastanova G.E.**
INSULIN-PRODUCING FUNCTION OF THE PANCREAS, LIPID PEROXIDATION
INDICATORS AND ANTIOXIDANT DEFENSE SYSTEMS IN RATS EXPOSED TO
LEAD.....336
50. **Zohidova S.H., Mamataliyev A.R.**
MORPHOLOGY OF EXTRAHEPATIC BILE DUCTS IN LABORATORY ANIMALS
AFTER EXPERIMENTAL REMOVAL OF THE GALLBLADDER.....340
51. **Khamidova F.M., Narzikulov Sh.F.**
MORPHORANGENOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF INFLAMMATORY
PROCESSES OF THE RESPIRATORY ORGANS.....346
52. **Davronova M.Sh., Ilyasov A.S., Avezov A.U., Aytimova G.Y.**
INFLUENCE OF ENERGY DRINKS ON MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF
THE PANCREAS.....358
53. **Khoshimov B.L., Akhmedova S.M.**
INFLUENCE OF METABOLIC SYNDROME ON ARTERIES.....363
54. **Babajanov T.Zh., Ilesov A.S., Avezov A.U., Aitimova G.Y.** IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL
ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES THAT DEVELOPED IN THE TISSUE
STRUCTURES OF THE DUODENUM UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF ENERGY
DRINKS.....375
55. **Babajanov T.Zh., Ilesov A.S., Avezov A.U., Aitimova G.Y.**
STUDY OF EFFECTS OF ENERGY DRINKS ON MORPHOLOGICAL AND
MORPHOMETRIC STATE OF DUODENAL TISSUE STRUCTURES IN RATS.....381
56. **Kurbanov G.T.**
PECULIARITIES OF THE ORGANIZATION AND STRUCTURE OF THE MAMMALIAN
RESPIRATORY TRACT.....388
57. **Juraev K.D., Islamov Sh.E.**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND PARAMETERS OF THE THYMUS
GLAND IN CHILDREN.....393
58. **Khasanova D.A., Azimova Z.S.**
FEATURES OF LUNG MORPHOLOGY UNDER INFLUENCE OF DYES AND ITS
PHYTCORRECTION.....401
59. **Samieva U. Gulnoza, Rakhmonov T. Sardor.**
PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF IRON DEFICIENCY IN HEART FAILURE.....411

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

60. **Nuritdinov U.A., Fattakhov R.A.**
ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH UNILATERAL ANTERIOR DISCLOSATION OF THE TMJ ARTICULAR DISC.....417

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

61. **Indiaminov S.I., Shoyimov Sh.U., Sagdullayev N.N.**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF HEAD STRUCTURE INJURIES IN PEDESTRIANS INJURED AS A RESULT OF COLLISIONS WITH MOVING VEHICLES.....424

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

62. **Bustanov Sh.Y.**
ETIO-PATHO-MORPHOGENESIS OF COVID-19 (LITERATURE REVIEW).....429
63. **Adjablaeva N. Dinara, Parpieva N. Nargiza**
STRUCTURE OF SOMATIC PATHOLOGY FEATURES OF EPIDEMIOLOGICAL HISTORY DURING THE DEVELOPMENT OF LTBI AND ITS PROGRESSION IN CHILDREN.....438

UROLOGY

64. **Allazov I.S., Allazov S. A.**
CYSTIC KIDNEY NEOPLASMS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....447
65. **Allazov S.A., Allazov I.S.**
MODERN VIEWS ON DIAGNOSTIC METHODS AND TREATMENT OF URINARY PERITONITIS.....458

PHARMACOLOGY

66. **Kasimova D.S., Vladimir A.A., Babich S.M., Khamrakulov Sh.Kh.**
CHANGES IN THE DIGESTABILITY OF STARCH DURING INTERACTION WITH FATS IN THE COMPOSITION OF STARCH-FAT SUBSTRATES.....466
67. **Kasimova D.S., Vladimir A.A., Babich S.M., Khamrakulov Sh.Kh.**
INFLUENCE OF FAT HYDROLYSATES ON CHANGES IN THE DIGESTABILITY OF STARCH IN THE COMPOSITION OF STARCH- FAT SUBSTRATES.....474

UDK 616.248-08

YAKUBOV Abdusalol Vahobovich

DSc. Professor

MUSAYEVA Lola Jurayevna

PhD

AKBAROVA Dilfuza Suratovna

PhD

SAIDOVA Shakhnoza Aripovna

PhD

ARIPDJANOVA Shaxlo Sardarovna

PhD

AVAZOVA Gulchekhra Nurillayevna

Tashkent Medical Academy

THE CURRENT ROLE OF MACROLYDES IN THE TREATMENT OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA

For citation: Yakubov A.V., Musayeva L.J., Akbarova D.S., Saidova Sh.A., Aripdjanova Sh.S., Avazova G.N. The current role of macrolides in the treatment of bronchial asthma. // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 5, pp.31-36

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14179172>

ANNOTATION

Despite the improvement of diagnosis and treatment, the prevalence and death rate of bronchial asthma in the world is increasing year by year. Modern domestic and foreign studies on the assessment of the level of effectiveness of antibacterial treatment in patients during exacerbation of bronchial asthma show conflicting results. The evidence for the effectiveness of macrolide therapy for asthma in adults is not well established and remains controversial. We analyzed literature data to investigate the efficacy and safety of macrolide treatment for asthma in adults and found that macrolide use may help reduce the frequency of exacerbations in eosinophilic, non-eosinophilic, and severe asthma exacerbations.

Key words: bronchial asthma, treatment, exacerbation of the disease, macrolide antibiotics

ЯКУБОВ Абдужалол Вахобович
Доктор медицинских наук, профессор
МУСАЕВА Лола Джураевна
Кандидат медицинских наук
АКБАРОВА Дилфуза Суратовна
Кандидат медицинских наук

САИДОВА Шахноза Ариповна
Кандидат медицинских наук
АРИПДЖАНОВА Шахло Сардаровна
Кандидат медицинских наук
АВАЗОВА Гульчехра Нуриллаевна
Ташкентская медицинская академия

СОВРЕМЕННАЯ РОЛЬ МАКРОЛИДОВ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ БРОНХИАЛЬНОЙ АСТМЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Несмотря на совершенствование диагностики и лечения, распространенность и смертность от бронхиальной астмы в мире с каждым годом увеличивается. Современные отечественные и зарубежные исследования по оценке уровня эффективности антибактериального лечения больных в период обострения бронхиальной астмы показывают противоречивые результаты. Доказательства эффективности терапии макролидами при астме у взрослых недостаточно изучены и остаются противоречивыми. Мы проанализировали литературные данные для изучения эффективности и безопасности лечения астмы макролидами у взрослых и обнаружили, что применение макролидов может помочь снизить частоту обострений при эозинофильных, неэозинофильных и тяжелых обострениях астмы.

Ключевые слова: бронхиальная астма, лечение, обострение заболевания, макролидные антибиотики.

YAKUBOV Abdusalol Vahobovich

t.f.d., professor

MUSAYEVA Lola Jurayevna

t.f.n.

AKBAROVA Dilfuza Suratovna

t.f.n.

SAIDOVA Shaxnoza Aripovna

t.f.n.

ARIPDJANOVA Shaxlo Sardarovna

t.f.n.

AVAZOVA Gulchehra Nurillayevna

Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi

BRONXIAL ASTMANI DAVOLASHDA MAKROLIDLARNING HOZIRGI O'RNI

ANNOTATSIYA

Diagnostika va davolashning yaxshilanishiga qaramay, dunyoda bronxial astmaning tarqalishi va o'lim darajasi yil sayin ortib bormoqda. Zamonaviy mahalliy va xorijiy tadqiqotlar bronxial astmaning kuchayish davrida bemorlarda antibakterial davolashning samaradorlik darajasini baholash qarama-qarshi natijalarni ko'rsatmoqda. Kattalardagi astma uchun makrolid davolashsining samaradorligi to'g'risida dalillar yaxshi o'rnatilmagan va bahsli bo'lib qolmoqda. Biz kattalardagi astma uchun makrolid davolashsining samaradorligi va xavfsizligini o'rganish uchun adabiyot ma'lumotlarini tahlil qildik va makrolidlardan foydalanish eozinofil, eozinofil bo'lmagan va astmaning og'ir shakllarining kuchayishi xavfi yuqori bo'lgan astmaning kuchayish chastotasini kamaytirishga yordam berishi mumkinligini aniqladik.

Kalit so'zlar: bronxial astma, davolash, kasallik zo'rayishi, makrolid antibiotiklari

Bronxial astma juda keng tarqalgan kasallikdir. So‘nggi yillarda olib borilgan epidemiologik tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, dunyo aholisining 4 dan 10 foizigacha turli darajadagi bronxial astma bilan og‘riydilar. Bronxial astma (BA) insoniyatning eng ilg‘or kasalliklaridan biridir. Respublika allergiya markazi ma‘lumotlariga ko‘ra, so‘nggi 5 yilda O‘zbekistonda bronxial astmaning og‘ir klinik ko‘rinishi bilan og‘rigan bemorlar soni 0,7 foizdan 17,5 foizga oshgan. Ma‘lumki, astma bilan bog‘liq kasallanish, o‘lim va sog‘liqni saqlash xarajatlarining aksariyati o‘tkir kuchayishlardan kelib chiqadi.

Davolash ikkita asosiy rejimni o‘z ichiga oladi - asosiy davolash va astmaning zo‘raygan davri uchun davolash. Asosiy davolash hajmi astmaning og‘irligi va nazorat darajasi, bemorlarning yoshi va birga keladigan patologiyaning tabiati bilan belgilanadi. Asosiy davolash ushbu kasallikni davolashda bosqichma-bosqich yondashuv tamoyilidan foydalangan holda belgilanadi [1]. Davolash darajasi qanchalik yuqori bo‘lsa, bemor shunchalik ko‘p nazorat dori-darmonlarini oladi va ularning dozalari shunchalik yuqori bo‘ladi. Dori vositalarini ingalatsiyalash astmani davolashning asosiy usuli hisoblanadi. Asosiy davolash bronxodilatator ta’sirga ega bo‘lgan dorilarni (uzoq ta’sir qiluvchi beta2-agonistlar, sekin chiqariladigan teofillin preparatlari) va yallig‘lanishga qarshi ta’sirga ega dorilarni (ingalyatsion glyukokortikosteroidlar, kromonlar, antileykotrienlar va antisitokinlar) o‘z ichiga oladi. Og‘ir va nazoratsiz astma tez-tez kuchayishi bilan birga keladi, bu bemorning hayot sifatiga salbiy ta’sir qiladi va davolash xarajatlarini oshiradi.

Makrolid antibiotiklari (makrolidlar) butun dunyo bo‘ylab eng ko‘p buyuriladigan antibiotiklar qatoriga kiradi va keng ko‘lamli infeksiyalar uchun ishlatiladi [2]. Dastlab, makrolidlar asosan yuqori nafas yo‘llarining infeksiyalarini, shuningdek teri va yumshoq to‘qimalar infeksiyalarini davolash uchun ishlatilgan. Hozirgi vaqtda makrolidlar gramm-musbat mikroorganizmlar (masalan, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus*) keltirib chiqaradigan infeksiyalarni davolash uchun va ba’zi gram-manfiylar (masalan, *Haemophilus influenzae*), shuningdek atipik (masalan, *Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*) mikroorganizmlar uchun ishlatiladi.

Makrolidlarning asosiy tuzilishi turli miqdordagi uglerod atomlarini o‘z ichiga olgan makrosiklik lakton halqasidan iborat. 14 a‘zoli makrolidlarga quyidagilar kiradi: eritromitsin, oleandomisin , klaritromitsin , roksitromitsin. Ketolidlar 14 a‘zoli makrolidlar bo‘lib , ularda keto guruhi lakton halqasiga birlashtirilgan. Telitromitsin preparati ushbu guruhga tegishli. Ketolidlar MDRSP (multidrug resistant *S. pneumoniae*), eritromitsinga chidamli va boshqa keng qo‘llaniladigan antibakterial preparatlarga nisbatan faoldir. Azalidlar 15 a‘zodan iborat 9 va 10-uglerod atomlari orasidagi 14 a‘zoli lakton halqasiga azot atomini kiritish orqali olingan makrosiklik struktura hisoblanadi. Bularga yagona dori azitromitsin kiradi (makrolidlar orasida *H. influenzae* ga qarshi eng faol preparatdir). 16 a‘zoli makrolidlarga quyidagi dorilar kiradi: midekamitsin, spiramitsin, josamitsin.

Makrolidlarning astmada samaradorligini o‘rganish uchun bir nechta yirik randomizatsiyalangan klinik sinovlar o‘tkazildi. Azitromitsin birinchi va rasmiy ravishda quyi nafas yo‘llarining infeksiyalari va bakterial etiologiyaning boshqa bir qator kasalliklari uchun qisqa 3 kunlik davolash kurslari shaklida foydalanish uchun tasdiqlangan.

3 ta tadqiqotning meta-tahlili asosida AZISAST, AZMATICS (597 bemor) astmada 3 yoki undan ortiq hafta davomida qo‘llangan makrolid antibiotiklarining samaradorligi bo‘yicha [4,5,6] makrolid davolash platsebo bilan solishtirganda eksperimental oqimning cho‘qqisi, simptomlar va hayot sifatining sezilarli yaxshilanishini aniqladi, lekin birinchi soniyada forsirlangan nafas chiqarish hajmiga sezilarli ta’sir ko‘rsatilmagan (FEV1). Tez-tez kuchaygan og‘ir astma bilan og‘rigan bemorlarda azitromitsinning samaradorligini o‘rganish eozinofil bo‘lmagan astma fenotipi bo‘lgan bemorlarda kasallik zo‘rayish chastotasining pasayishini aniqladi. Azitromitsinni qo‘llashda bemorlarning umumiy guruhida ham (nisbiy xavf (NX) 0,61; 95% ishonch oralig‘i (IO) 0,49-0,78; $p < 0,001$) va eozinofil bo‘lmagan kichik guruhlarda ham astma kuchayishi chastotasining pasayishi kuzatildi. (NX 0,61; 95% IO 0,45-0,82; $p = 0,001$), eozinofil (NX 0,63; 95% IO 0,44-0,92; $p = 0,015$) va og‘ir (NX 0,69; 95% IO = 20; 95% CI; 0,013) BA. Azitromitsin bilan uzoq muddatli davolash olgan bemorlarda kuzatuv davrida ham umumiy kohortda (imkoniyat nisbati (IN) 0,58; 95% IO 0,41-

0,82; $p = 0,002$) ham, eozinofilli kichik guruhda ham astmaning kuchayishi ehtimoli kamroq bo'ldi. (IN 0,48; 95% IO 0,28-0,81; $p = 0,006$). Eozinofil bo'lmagan yoki og'ir astma bilan og'rigan bemorlarda astma kuchayishi ehtimoli kamroq edi, ammo guruhlar o'rtasidagi farq statistik jihatdan ahamiyatli emas edi. Kuzatuv davrida keyingi kuchayishgacha bo'lgan vaqt umumiy kohortda (salbiy natija xavfi - NX 0,71; 95% IO 0,56-0,91; $p = 0,007$) va eozinofil BA (NX 0,67) bo'lgan kichik guruhda sezilarli darajada farq qildi. IO 0,45-0,98; $p = 0,038$). Preparatni qabul qilishning eozinofil bo'lmagan va og'ir astmaga ta'siri statistik ahamiyatga ega emas edi. Azitromitsin va platsebo guruhleri o'rtasida ingolyatsion kortikosteroidlarini buyurish chastotasi umumiy guruhda ham, eozinofil bo'lmagan yoki og'ir astmada ham sezilarli darajada farq qilmadi. Azitromitsin bilan davolash astma bilan bog'liq hayot sifatini sezilarli darajada yaxshilamadi. Astma so'rovlariga ko'ra astma nazorati darajasi Asthma Control Questionnaire (astma nazorati uchun so'rovnoma) va Asthma Quality of Life Questionnaire (astma bilan og'rigan bemorlarning hayot sifatini baholash uchun so'rovnoma), shuningdek o'pka funktsiyasi ko'rsatkichlari, periferik qon va balg'amdagi eozinofillar va neytrofillar soni kabi parametrlar, shuningdek nojo'ya ta'sirlar kuzatuv davrida azitromitsin va platsebo guruhleri o'rtasida farq qilmadi.

Shunday qilib, ushbu meta-tahlil shuni ko'rsatdiki, azitromitsin bilan uzoq muddatli parvarishlash davolashi eozinofil va eozinofil bo'lmagan, shuningdek og'ir astma kuchayishini kamaytiradi. Azitromitsinni qabul qilish eozinofil astma bilan og'rigan bemorlarda ingolyatsion kortikosteroidlar kurslarining chastotasini kamaytirishga yordam berdi va eozinofil bo'lmagan va og'ir astmada antibiotiklarga bo'lgan ehtiyojni kamaytirdi, ammo astma nazorati darajasiga, hayot sifatiga, o'pka funktsiyasiga va qondagi eozinofillar soniga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmadi. va Azitromitsin bemorlar tomonidan yaxshi qabul qilingan. Davolashga uzoq vaqt davomida azitromitsin qo'shilishi astma bilan og'rigan bemorlarda kasallik zo'rayish xavfini kamaytirishi mumkin.

AZALEA klinik tadqiqoti [7] astmaning o'tkir kuchayishi bo'lgan bemorlarda standart davolashga peroral azitromitsinni qo'shish statistik jihatdan ahamiyatli yoki klinik jihatdan muhim ta'sir ko'rsatmasligini ko'rsatdi. Ko'p darajali modellastirishdan foydalangan holda, 10-kundagi guruhlar o'rtasida simptomlar ko'rsatkichlarida statistik jihatdan muhim farq yo'q edi. Bundan tashqari, boshlang'ich va 10-kun o'rtasida kasallik simptomlari bo'yicha guruhlar o'rtasida sezilarli farqlar yo'q edi. Har qanday kunda AQLQ, Mini AQLQ yoki o'pka funktsiyasining har qanday o'lchovlarida guruhlar o'rtasida sezilarli farqlar yo'q edi va simptomlar ko'rsatkichlarining 50% ga qisqarishi uchun vaqt bo'yicha farqlar yo'q edi. Buning sababi, astmaning kuchayishi uchun antibiotik davolashdan potentsial foyda ko'rish mumkin bo'lgan bemorlarning tadqiqotdan chiqarilishi bo'lishi mumkin, chunki ular allaqachon antibiotik qabul qilgan. Shuning uchun antibiotiklar buyurilmaganlar antibiotiklarning yaroqliligi uchun juda salbiy tanlangan bo'lishi mumkin.

2024 yil mart, Respiratory Investigation (Elsevier) jurnalida tizimli ko'rib chiqish va meta-tahlil natijalarini e'lon qildi, unda olimlar makrolidlarning bronxial astmani davolashda samarali va xavfsiz ekanligini baholadilar. Meta-tahlil 918 bemor bilan 7 ta randomizatsiyalangan klinik sinovlarni [4,6,8,9,10,11,12] o'z ichiga olgan. Bemorlar ikki guruhga bo'lingan: Tadqiqot guruhi - turli dozalarda makrolid guruhidan qabul qildi. Nazorat guruhi - makrolid bilan taqqoslanadigan dozada platsebo oldi. Oltita sinovda bemorlar azitromitsinni turli dozalar rejimlarida qabul qilishdi (odatda kuniga kamida 200 mg ga ekvivalent). Bir tadqiqotda bemorlarga kuniga ikki marta 500 mg klaritromitsin qabul qilingan. Eng qisqa kuzatuv davri 6 hafta, maksimal 48 hafta edi. Tadqiqot guruhi va nazorat guruhidagi bemorlarda bronxial astmaning kuchayishi epizodlari soni taqqoslangan (NX = 0,71; 95% IO 0,46-1,09; $p = 0,12$). Shu bilan birga, makrolidlarni qabul qilgan bemorlarda platseboga nisbatan quyidagi afzalliklar qayd etilgan. Makrolidlar bilan nojo'ya dori reaksiyalarining tezligi platsebodan yuqori emas edi (NX = 0,61; 95% IO 0,34-1,10; $p = 0,10$). Ushbu meta-tahlil shuni ko'rsatdiki, kattalardagi astma uchun makrolid terapiyasi platsebo bilan solishtirganda qisqa ta'sir qiluvchi bronxodilatatorlar iste'molini sezilarli darajada kamaytirdi. Uzoq muddatli, past dozali makrolid davolashini olgan bemorlarning kichik guruhlar tahlili platsebo bilan solishtirganda ACQ va AQLQ ko'rsatkichlarida sezilarli yaxshilanishlarni ko'rsatdi. Ushbu tadqiqotning foydasi

shundaki, u kattalardagi astma uchun makrolid davolashsining samaradorligi va xavfsizligi haqidagi ilmiy dalillarni yangilaydi [13].

Makrolidlar antibakterial dorilar guruhi ichida eng xavfsiz va yaxshi qabul qilinadigan dorilar hisoblanadi. Biroq, ulardan foydalanish bir qator salbiy dori reaksiyalarini keltirib chiqarishi mumkin, masalan diareya, jigar yetishmovchiligi, QT oralig'ining oshishi, ko'plab dori vositalarining o'zaro ta'siri bilan bog'liq bo'lgan CYP3A4 sitoxromini bloklash [14]. Diareya eng keng tarqalgan peroral qabul qilinganda makrolidlarning nojo'ya ta'siridir. Makrolidlarni qo'llashda transaminazalar darajasi asimptomatik engil o'sish 1-5% hollarda kuzatiladi, bu kamdan-kam hollarda dozalash rejimini o'zgartirishni yoki to'xtatishni talab qiladi. Kamdan-kam hollarda eritromitsin, klaritromitsin, azitromitsin va telitromitsin qo'llash jigar shikastlanishi holatlari masalan, xolestatik gepatit va gepatotsellyulyar yetishmovchiligi kuzatilishi mumkin. Ko'pincha makrolidlar qayta buyurilganda gepatotoksik ta'sir kuzatilishi mumkin. Sariqlik bilan gepatotsellyulyar shikastlanish o'tkir jigar yetishmovchiligiga olib kelishi mumkin va hatto o'limga olib kelishi mumkin. Ushbu turdagi jigar shikastlanishi ko'pincha telitromitsin bilan, ba'zan azitromitsin va kamroq hollarda klaritromitsin va eritromitsin bilan sodir bo'ladi. Makrolidlarni qo'llash elektrokardiogrammada (EKG) QT oralig'ining oshishi va makrolidlar kaliy kanallarini bloklashi natijasida piruet taxikardiyaga sabab bo'lishi mumkin. Azitromitsin QT oralig'ining >450 ms uzayishi, yurak aritmiyasi va eshitish qobiliyati past bo'lgan bemorlarga tavsiya etilmaydi.

Ko'pgina tadqiqotlar (89%) gastrointestinal nojo'ya ta'sirlar (ko'ngil aynishi, qorin og'rig'i, diareya) haqida xabar berdi [4,7,9,13]. Adabiyotlarni o'rganish shuni ko'rsatdiki, azitromitsin astma bilan og'rikan bemorlarda platsebo bilan solishtirganda oshqozon-ichak traktining nojo'ya ta'sirini sezilarli darajada oshirmagan, bu astma bilan og'rikan bemorlarda azitromitsin bilan davolash xavfsiz ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Biroq, makrolidlardan uzoq muddatli foydalanish kelajakda chidamli bakteriyalar xavfini oshirishi mumkin. Bryussel [4] azitromitsin bilan uzoq muddatli davolanish makrolidlarga chidamli orofaringeal streptokokklarning oshishiga olib kelishini, Gibson esa [9] ikki davolash guruhi o'rtasida sezilarli farq yo'qligini aniqladi.

Astmaga qarshi monoklonal antitana dorilarning paydo bo'lishini hisobga olsak, og'ir eozinofil astmada makrolidlarning roli ham shubhali. Makrolidlar og'ir eozinofil bo'lmagan astma uchun ham buyurilishi mumkin.

Makrolidlarning ijobiy ta'siri bir nechta komponentlar bilan belgilanadi: to'g'ridan-to'g'ri antibakterial ta'sir; nospetsifik yallig'lanishga qarshi ta'sir; shilliq ajralishini kamaytirish; bronxial giperreaktivlikni kamaytirish; ularning o'tkazuvchanligini yaxshilash va buning natijasida kasallik simptomlarini kamaytirish. Makrolidlarni qo'llash eozinofil, eozinofil bo'lmagan va astmaning og'ir shakllarining kuchayishi chastotasini kamaytirishga yordam beradi.

IQTIBOSLAR | ЧОККИ | REFERENCES:

1. Avdeev S.N., Belevskiy A.S., Aisanov Z.R. Bronxial astma bilan og'rikan bemorlarni tanishtirish uchun yangi yondashuvlar va algoritm. Amaliy pulmonologiya. 2019;1:3-5.
2. Hansen M., Scott A., McCullough A. va boshqalar. Har qanday ko'rsatkich uchun platseboga qarshi makrolid antibiotiklarini qabul qilgan odamlarda noxush hodisalar. Cochrane ma'lumotlar bazasi tizimi Rev. 2019 yil 18-yanvar ;1 (1):CD011825. doi : 10.1002/14651858.CD011825.
3. Yudina L.V. Bronxial astmaning yuqumli kuchayishida azitromitsindan foydalanish . Ukraina salomatligi. 2015;2:3
4. Brusselle G., VanderStichele C., Jordens P., Deman R., Slabbynck H., Ringoet V. va boshqalar. Og'ir astmada kuchayishning oldini olish uchun azitromitsin (AZISAST): ko'p markazli randomizatsiyalangan ikki tomonlama ko'r platsebo - nazorat ostida sinov. Toraks 2013 ;68 (4):322 - 9.
5. Reiter J, Demirel N, Mendy A va boshqalar. Astmani uzoq muddatli davolash uchun makrolidlar - randomizatsiyalangan klinik sinovlarning meta-tahlili. Allergiya 2013; DOI: 10.1111/all.12199.

6. Hahn DL, Grasmick M, Hetzel S, Yale S; AZMATICS (AZithroMycin - Jamiyat sozlamalarida astma bo'yicha sinov) o'quv guruhi. Kattalardagi bronxial astma uchun azitromitsin: samaradorlik sinovi. *J Am Board Fam Med* 2012 ;25:442 –59.
7. Jonston S., Szigeti M., Cross M. va boshqalar. Astmaning o'tkir kuchayishi bilan og'rigan kattalardagi bemorlar uchun standart yordamga qo'shimcha sifatida og'iz azitromitsinning samaradorligini baholash uchun randomizatsiyalangan, ikki tomonlama ko'r, platsebo-nazoratli tadqiqot (AZALEA sinovi) . Sautgempton (Buyuk Britaniya): NIHR Journals Library; 2016 ; 3 .
8. Cameron EJ, Chaudhuri R, Mair F, McSharry C, Greenlaw N, Weir CJ va boshqalar. Astma bilan kasallangan chekuvchilarda azitromitsinning tasodifiy nazorat ostida sinovi. *evro Respira J* ; 2013 (42): 1412-1415.
9. Gibson P., Yang I., Upham J. va boshqalar. Azitromitsinning doimiy nazoratsiz astma (AMAZES) bilan og'rigan kattalardagi astma kuchayishi va hayot sifatiga ta'siri: randomizatsiyalangan , ikki marta ko'r , platsebo-nazorat ostidagi sinov. *Lancet*.2017 ;390 ;659-668.
10. Hahn DL, Plane MB ,. Mahdi OS, Byrne GI. Uchuvchining ikkinchi darajali natijalari
11. astma PloS uchun azitromitsinni davolashning randomizatsiyalangan sinovi Klin sinovlari. 2006 ;1: 11 .
12. Sadeghdoust M., Mirsadraee M., Aligolighasemabadi F. , Xakzad MR, Hashemi A., Naghibi S. Azitromitsinning og'ir doimiy astmada bronxial devor qalinligiga ta'siri: er-xotin ko'r platsebo-nazoratli randomizatsiyalangan klinik sinov. *Respir Med* 2021 ;185:4 -9.
13. Sutherland ER, King TS, Icitovic N., BT Ameredes , E. Bleecker, HA Boushey va boshqalar. Suboptimal nazorat ostida astmani davolash uchun klaritromitsinning sinovi . *J Allergiya klinikasi Immunol* 2010 ;126:747 -753.
14. Fukuda Yosuke, Horita Nobuyuki, Aga Masaharu . Katta yoshdagi astma uchun makrolid davolashining samaradorligi va xavfsizligi: tizimli tahlil va meta-tahlil. *Nafas olish organlarini tekshirish* . 2024; 62 (2): 206-215 .
15. Vestfal JF. Makrolid tomonidan induktsiyalangan P-450A (CYP) 3A4 sitoxromi bilan klinik ahamiyatga ega dori o'zaro ta'siri: klaritromitsin, azitromitsin va diritromitsinga qaratilgan yangilanish . *Britaniyalik Klinl J Farmakol* . 2000 ; 50 (4): 285-95.
16. Moseley RH. Makrolid antibiotiklari. Antimikrobiyal va antifungal vositalarning hepatotoksitesisi. In: *Giyohvand moddalardan kelib chiqqan jigar kasalligi*. Kaplowitz N, DeLeve LD, muharrirlar. 3- nashr. Amsterdam, NL: Elsevier; 2013: 466-7.
17. Choi Y, Lim HS, Chung D, Choi J, Yoon D. Haqiqiy amaliyotda azitromitsin tomonidan qo'zg'atilgan QT uzayishi xavfini baholash. *BioMed Research International*. 2018. doi : 10.1155/2018/1574806.

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 5

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 5

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000